

RESEARCH OF THE HISTORY OF KASHKADARYA OASIS IN ANCIENT SOURCES.

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ANNOTATION This article tells about the ancient history of the Kashkadarya River, which supplies water to the Kashkadarya oasis. Information about the territory and its geographical location is analyzed.

KEY WORDS: Keshk-Rud, Sogd, Source, Gava, Gavmard, History.

Outside our country, the first written sources related to the history of our country were recorded - "Avesta", cuneiform inscriptions of the Achaemenid period and sources relating to the ancient world (Greco-Roman) period. They were the first in the history of the Ancient East and the world to learn about the names of the ancient peoples of our country, the names of special places, mountains, rivers, lakes, the names of legendary heroes and kings, about the way of life, religion, customs, culture, socio-economic and political system of the peoples of our countries containing ring information. Due to the scarcity of these sources, to study ancient political and socio-economic processes it is necessary to turn to written and archaeological sources. Archaeological data obtained through many years of research complement existing written sources and show clear directions of historical development.[1]

Kashkadarya oasis (Southern Sogd) is one of the ancient historical and geographical regions of Central Asia. The Kashkadarya oasis is located at the intersection of ancient trade routes. Information about this area is also covered in written sources.

It can be assumed that the concepts of Gava, Gau ("the place where the Sugdians live"), Gava Sugda ("the place of the Sugdians"), mentioned in the Avesta, refer to the oasis of Kashkadarya (or the eastern part). region). This word itself is related to Gavdara, Gavtepe, Govkhona, Gavmard, Govmarda, Govmardtepe, Gav mountains, Gav peak and other words of the eastern part of Kashkadarya (Kitob, Shakhrisabz, Yakkabog and Chirakchi regions), which have been preserved in many modern terms. . They have come down to us in most cases in the form of names of places, spaces and villages. Ahuramazda, the great and wise god of Zoroastrianism, mentions that he founded the place "Gava Sugda" along with many lands. In the book "Videvdat" of the Avesta, agriculture is considered a commendable work: "Whoever cultivates the land, O Spitama

Zarathushtra, with his left and right hand, with his right and left hand, is said to benefit the earth" (Videvdat, Chapter 3).[2]

In 545-540 BC, the Achaemenids subjugated the regions of Parthia, Margiana, Bactria and Sugdiana in Central Asia. Cuneiform inscriptions of the Achaemenid period contain various information about the peoples and regions of Central Asia. These inscriptions date back to the 6th-4th centuries BC and are written in Old Persian. During this period, the history of the peoples of Central Asia is also well covered in the works of ancient Greek historians.

Particularly valuable in this regard are Herodotus's "History" and other parts that give a brief but very accurate description of the peoples of Central Asia. According to Herodotus, the horn of Darius I divided the Achaemenid state into 20 regions. Herodotus reports about Central Asia:

History, Book III, 92. "The peoples from the Bactrians to the Aegylians paid a tax of 300 talents. This is the twelfth country.

History, Book III, 93. "Saki and Caspian paid a tax of 200 talents. This is the fifteenth country." "The Parthians, Khorezmians, Sugdians and Aryans paid a tax of 300 talents. This is the sixteenth land" (One talent - 33,655 kg of silver).[3]

Thus, on the basis of the given written, historical, topographical and geographical data, a conclusion was made about the existence of the ancient name of the Kashkadarya river both in Chinese written sources and in Turkic ones.

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